

GENRE FEATURES OF ART PROSE G. MULLER

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Abstract: Herta Muller is one of the last German writers to receive the Nobel Prize in Literature. This fact draws special attention to the writer's work when studying the latest trends in German-language literature, since in his works the head allegedly believes that people should only live happily in the world.

Keywords: Genre, meta-genre, autofigure, autofantastic.

G. MYULLER BADIY ADABIYOTINING JANR XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Gerta Myuller adabiyot bo'yicha Nobel mukofotiga sazovor bo'lgan so'nggi nemis adiblaridan biridir. Bu fakt nemis tilidagi adabiyotning so'nggi yo'nalishlarini o'rganishda yozuvchi ijodiga alohida e'tibor qaratadi, chunki uning asarlarida bosh go'ya dunyoda insonlar faqat baxtli yashashligi kerakligi asosiy ustivor masala hisobladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Janr, metajanr, avtofikr, avtofantastika.

**ЖАНРОВЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОЙ ПРОЗЫ Г.
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Аннотация: Герта Мюллер-один из последних немецких писателей, получивших Нобелевскую премию по литературе. Этот факт обращает особое внимание на творчество писателя при изучении последних направлений немецкоязычной литературы, так как в своих произведениях голова якобы считает, что в мире люди должны жить только счастливо.

Ключевые слова: Жанр, метажанр, автофикр, автофантастика.

In the study of Herta Müller's prose, it is important to take into account, on the one hand, the originality of the writer's work within the genres declared when the works were published, and, on the other hand, lacunae and ambiguities in the genre identification of her individual works. In the first case, consideration of the genre nomination provides the key to reading the work in the context of a certain genre tradition, to considering its contribution to the development of the genre. In the second case, the task of detecting the features of historical genres in genre-undefined works and, accordingly, the contents inherent in these genres, their deformation in works, is revealed. At the same time, one should not lose sight of the fact that the author's refusal from the genre nomination (or ignoring it) should be understood as an apophatic manifestation of genre identification, in which the work is placed outside the genre framework [1,48-51], [1,76-83].

Published under the editorship of Norbert Otto Ecke, the monograph on Hertha Müller divides the prose works of the writer into nonfiction and fiction, where the latter are divided into early prose and novels. The same division is proposed by Julia Müller in her work “Language tact. The Literary Style of Herta Müller. Thus, the researchers divide the artistic prose of Herta Müller into two blocks. The first, "early" block, is filled with works of small volume created by the writer in the period from 1978 to 1986. The genre definition of the works of the second, “late” block is designated by the authors of both monographs as a novel. However, Gudrun Lorints points out that during the publication of works, the designation of genres was carried out as follows:

“So, “The Lowlands” and “Barefoot February” are designated as prose, “A man in this world is a big pheasant” and “Painful Tango” as a story, “The Fox was already a hunter then”, “Heart-beast”, “Today I would I never met myself better” and “Swing of Breath” as novels, and “Hunger and Silk” and “Trapped” as essays. At the same time, “The Devil sits in the mirror”, “The King bows and kills”, “Always the same snow and always the same uncle” without a generic [and genre] definition” [2-117].

For the researcher, the division into journalistic and literary texts is conditional. She believes that the unified format for the publication of publicistic and fiction prose by Herta Müller in the Fischer publishing house equalizes them, puts them on a par. Books by Herta Müller in the specified publishing house are united by a selection of illustrations for covers that have a common theme, style and graphic designer. This argument seems unconvincing: the actions of the publisher and the artist do not seek and do not have the opportunity to equate artistic and journalistic works in literary discourse, since they have other motives. The publisher published Müller's works in 2009 with a uniform cover style in order to make it easier for the reader to find and purchase books by the writer, who gained great fame this year. However, Lorinz, like Lin Marven, considers the literary and non-fictional texts of Herta Müller as a single text and removes the barrier between them, referring to their auto-fictionality. Gudrun Lörinz refers here to autofiction as a genre that synthesizes the autobiographical and

the fictional in narrative [3-21]. Autofictionality, according to the researcher, problematizes the genre of the texts: “autofictional writing is characterized by a mixture of genders and genres” [4-117]. However, it is worth noting that autofiction is neither opposed nor on the same level with the novel. Autofiction is a fairly broad supra-genre concept, and represents a specific relationship to the content and the described reality of the work. It is connected with the modality of the utterance, and not with the specific formal content features of a particular genre. Therefore, an autofictional text can have a different genre definition and, accordingly, is a metagenre. If, for example, the autobiographically based "Tombstone" and "Rotten Pears" can be defined as short stories, then "Heart-Beast" or "The Fox was already a hunter then" are novels.

The "authenticity claim" that exists in autofiction is not about the authenticity of the facts of objective reality, but the personal emotional experience of the writer or, to use the terminology of Herta Müller, not the events themselves, but their “insides”, which are difficult to catch in the act of imprinting them in the text. Thus, autobiography rejects the non-fictional utterance of an autobiography, not because the utterance seems insufficiently reliable, but precisely because autofiction shifts attention from facts to emotional experience. Autofiction does not so much exist due to the tension between the authentic and the fictional (this tension is present in the meta-genre between the image of the author and the content that does not correspond to his "biography"), but rather recognizes the fictitious's right to authenticity, since fiction is another way of conveying personal experience.

Herta Müller's work in the autofiction meta-genre can be placed in a broader context. The active appeal to autobiography and increased attention to the construction of the image of the author is associated with a reassessment of values in the German-language literature of the second half of the 20th century. It was the result of a departure from the generalization in understanding the world that dominates the German intellectual and modernist novel. According to N.S. Pavlova, after the collapse of the

Third Reich, “the very concreteness of life, that reflection of life in the forms of life itself, the need for which the philosophical novel did not always have won its rights” [5-273]. The researcher believes that in post-war Germany, “writers considered it necessary to reflect the experience during the Second World War and after it” [6-274]. Autobiographical material began to be actively used in German-language literature. It has been used in different ways by different authors. Ilse Eichinger's novel *The Great Hope*, Monica Maron's novel *Flying Ash*, the novels of Marlina Streruvitz and Libuše Monikova are close or related to autofiction, since in their novels, connected with personal search and focused on the transfer of emotional experience, the figures of characters and narrators resonate with the image of the author.

The primacy of the transmission of personal experience over abstract philosophizing was preserved at the end of the century. E.V. Sokolova emphasizes that the German-language literature of the late twentieth century reflected a “turn towards man”:

“Intertextuality loses its former meaning: the experiences of a particular person are presented as unique, not requiring analogies and allusions (J. Frank, I. Schulze, G. Klein)... The provoking seriousness of the “new authors” in relation to themselves and the world around them is partly explained the fact that, from their point of view, there is nothing more important than "simple" stories about human life... The world is not so big for them - and they write for the whole world. First of all, about yourself” [7-34].

Among the bright authors of this turn we can name V.G. Sebald and W. Bucher, in whose works the narrator merges with the image of the author, and the plots echo the biographies of the authors. The creative comprehension of his own autobiography was also reflected in Gunter Grass's novel *The Bulb of Memory*.

Thus, the appeal to the autofiction meta-genre seems to be one of the signs of such a trend in German-language literature as a return to the “concreteness of life” and the primacy of subjectivity over abstract philosophizing. Autofiction offers the reader a number of possibilities.

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